

My name is Kamanuru Kiran Kumar and I was born in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh. During my childhood, my father had to go to some cities for professional work, part of which was when we were in Addanki. When I was studying in 3rd standard in a private school in Addanaki, my teacher told another teacher that he had received a letter that was full of numbers, and that it was written in a code language (the language of numbers). I heard, Since then I have had a wish. It may have been about 40 years since that happened. It is with that desire that the Marulipi (for English) was invented in the year 2001 and the Marulipi alphabet (for Telugu) was invented in the year 2024.

ಮಂಜುಲಿ ವರ್ಣಮಾಲೆ

ಅಕ್ಷರ ಮೂಲ ಸುಲಂಟಾಲೆ

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Kiran
02/06/2021

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మాణులు వర్ణముల

పాటలు - 2, 3, 4

క శీ క	క శీ క	క శీ క	క శీ క	క శీ క
చ శీ క	చ శీ క	చ శీ క	చ శీ క	చ శీ క
ట శీ క	ట శీ క	ట శీ క	ట శీ క	ట శీ క
త శీ క	త శీ క	త శీ క	త శీ క	త శీ క
ప శీ క	ప శీ క	ప శీ క	ప శీ క	ప శీ క
య శీ క	య శీ క	య శీ క	య శీ క	య శీ క
స శీ క	స శీ క	స శీ క	స శీ క	స శీ క
ఓ శీ క	ఓ శీ క	ఓ శీ క	ఓ శీ క	ఓ శీ క

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